

Relevant problems and optimized development path of football major macro development mechanism talent training in Chengdu University of Technology Physical Education University under the background of integration of sports and education

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Abstract: The concept of integration of sports and education is the overall planning and top-level design of China's education and sports work in the new era, which has an important guiding role in the reform of school sports in China. In the context of the integration of sports and education, this paper examines the current situation of football professional training in six ordinary undergraduate colleges in China, and provides reference for the development of Chengdu University of Technology's football program and the entire sports specialty. The focus of the transformation of ideas for the training of football professionals in colleges and universities lies in how to manage to govern, establish a staggered governance of sharing interests and responsibilities, and ensure the innovation of the operation guarantee system in terms of policies, systems and funds. It provides reference for the development of curve overtaking in the School of Physical Education of Chengdu University of Technology. The College of Physical Education of Chengdu University of Technology should integrate existing resources in combination with its own school running conditions to provide effective assistance for accelerating the construction of a new development pattern of the world's "double first-class" higher education schools of Chengdu University of Technology.

Keywords: Integration of sports and education; Football; Development mechanism; Talent cultivation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, the General Administration of Sport of the People's Republic of China held the "Sports Cup" three major league matches in Chinese cities in succession in various provinces and cities. It is hoped that the popularity of the games will be increased, a good sports atmosphere will be created, more people will be radiated, mass sports will be promoted, people will be satisfied with the sports for all, and the development of China's three major sports will be driven. Among all sports events, the three major sports events attract the most attention. Relatively speaking, China's three major sports events also have the largest development potential and rising space, and also have the largest attention and audience groups. In the current form and conditions, the development of the three major sports events is still an important breakthrough for the development of college sports colleges. As one of the important components of the annual campus sports activities in

Sichuan Province, the annual selection activity of the best line-up of Sichuan youth campus football held by the Education Department of Sichuan Province is of great significance in terms of promoting the reputation of colleges and universities and exploring the talent training model in the football industry. Nowadays, the development of the football specialty of college sports colleges has made great development and breakthrough in recent years, providing many football professionals for the development of China's football industry, and providing talent protection for the development of China's football industry. It has become an indispensable part of the development of China's football industry. After the campus football slogan was put forward, after five years of development, many colleges and universities not only focus on the enrollment and training of football projects, but also set up football colleges one after another. It is of great practical significance for the development of the football major of Chengdu Institute of Technology to examine the current talent training status of China's football specific training objectives, core courses, professional teachers, etc.

2. RESEARCH OBJECTS

This research makes a comparative study between the current situation of football professional training in Chengdu University of Technology and that in six ordinary undergraduate colleges in China. According to the time of establishment and scale of operation, six representative colleges and universities, namely Chengdu University Football Institute, Tongji University International Football Institute, Nanjing Sports Institute Football Institute, Wuhan Sports Institute Football Institute, Guangzhou Sports Institute Football Institute and Changchun Guanghua Football Institute, were selected for investigation. That is to say, under the macro background of the integration of sports and education, analyze the actual situation and the expected state of the current football professional training in ordinary undergraduate colleges and universities in China, and propose ways and methods to improve the training of football professionals in colleges and universities in China.

3. OVERVIEW OF EXISTING PROBLEMS OF FOOTBALL MAJOR IN CHINA

After reviewing the training plans for football professionals in six colleges and universities, all colleges and universities have been able to determine a clear training direction based on the actual situation of talent training, and can reflect the talent training objectives of football majors in the top-level design. However, the following problems can be seen in the comprehensive talent training program and talent training objectives:

3.1 The talent training goal is single, and the development concept orientation remains to be defined

3.1.1 Convergence of training objectives

Through the analysis of the training objectives of football major in six colleges and universities through retrieval and query, it is found that although the training objectives have different expressions, their actual contents are almost the same. The training objectives are mostly applied talents such as football teachers, football coaches or referees. As far as the training objectives of the football specialty of the Physical Education Institute are concerned, there is not much innovation, and it does not reflect the advantages of the school and the characteristics of football specialty training. At present, the positions of football teachers in primary and secondary schools are gradually saturated, the training objectives are too single, and the homogenization and assimilation problems are highlighted, which will inevitably lead to the increasingly fierce competition among football graduates. The training of football specialty should not only undertake the task of training football teachers, but also rely on the characteristics of school running to cultivate diversified football talents.

Table 1: Comparison of the training objectives of football professionals in ordinary undergraduate universities

College name	train objective
Wuhan University of Sport	Cultivate with good ideological and moral accomplishment and science and technology, to master the football skills and teaching and training methods, preliminary football special scientific research ability, to meet the needs of sports development in the new period, in schools, sports team and club college and other departments engaged in teaching, training, competition and management of applied talents.
Guangzhou University of Sport	On the basis of inheriting the original training goals of sports education and sports training majors, more attention is paid to training applied talents who can undertake the campus football work under the new situation.

Nanjing University of Sport	To cultivate application-oriented football specialized talents with all-round development of moral, intellectual and physical development, master modern sports science theories and methods, have football-relevant professional skills and practical ability, and can be competent for school physical education teaching, innovation consciousness and others with high social adaptability.
Tongji University	To cultivate systematic basic theories and basic knowledge of football training, physical fitness, injury, rehabilitation, nutrition and other aspects, master solid professional knowledge and modern football science training practice ability, and be competent for football training teaching, scientific research, management and other aspects. With the characteristics of Tongji football, boosting the revitalization and development of Chinese football, both the international vision of football elites and senior professional talents leading the development of football professional talents.
Chengdu University	Cultivate good ideological quality, solid theory, practical innovation ability, to adapt to the needs of modern campus football development, on the basis of comprehensive development of expertise, competent school football sports education, teaching, training and game organization, and can engage in school sports scientific research, school sports management, social sports guidance and other work of high-quality sports education applied talents.
Changchun Guanghua College	Market-oriented, cultivating the all-round development of morality, intelligence, physique and beauty, with strong practical ability and innovative spirit of football school, systematically mastering the basic theory, basic knowledge and basic skills of physical education, and can be competent for school sports teaching, extracurricular sports activities, after-school sports training and Italian competition work. And can be engaged in social sports guidance and management and other work of the applied undergraduate talents.

3.1.2 Lack of forward-looking development orientation

Based on the survey, the football majors in six colleges and universities in China attach great importance to talent training and have formulated special training programs, but the formulation of the development concept of football talent training lacks foresight. The education of football specialty is not only to cultivate campus football teachers and coaches, but also to cultivate football industry talents to meet the diversified needs of the market. Since the university education system is about four years, the cycle is long, and the employment situation is changeable now. If the talent training objectives are not forward-looking, it will lead to the derailment of graduates' ability from social needs and lack of market competitiveness.

3.2 Major structure setting lags behind and curriculum system development needs to be strengthened

As a major sports specialty, it needs reasonable enrollment specialty and scale. At present, the overall enrollment scale of the football specialty in colleges and universities and even the football colleges in some colleges and universities is small. On the one hand, it reflects that the football specialty is in the exploration period of development. On the other hand, it is also to ensure the source of students, implement small class teaching, and improve the quality of talents. The main purpose of the innovation of football specific professional setting is to break through the shackles of the original training mode of sports football talents and cultivate high-quality football talents with one specialty and many abilities, so as to provide talent support for the upgrading of China's football industry structure. At present, football majors are homogenized with the original majors of sports in terms of specialty setting.

At present, the unreasonable curriculum system for football majors is mainly reflected in two aspects: curriculum objectives and core courses. The problems in the curriculum objectives are reflected in the following three aspects: on the one hand, there is a certain difference between the curriculum objectives and the actual professional needs, and the degree of practice of the curriculum should be more in-depth. Secondly, the social needs and professional ability requirements should be considered, and the development status of the football industry should be thoroughly understood and mastered, and the curriculum system should be updated in the practical teaching and research. On the other hand, the proportion of courses is not balanced enough, and students' practical teaching ability is not emphasized. Secondly, the differentiation of core courses is not high. Core courses play an important role in the training of football professionals. After comparing the core courses of six schools, it is found that the teaching of each football major is not very different in the core courses and does not jump out of the shackles of the original training mode.

Figure 1: Credit ratio of football major students in each university

3.3 The construction of teaching staff is weak, and the contradiction between students' learning and training needs to be resolved

Teachers are the fundamental guarantee of talent training in colleges and universities. Teachers' knowledge reserves and teaching level directly determine the realization of professional talent training objectives. The development of football can not be separated from the continuous optimization and improvement of the level of teachers. In 2018, the Ministry of Education released the National Standards for the Teaching Quality of Undergraduate Specialty in Ordinary Colleges and Universities, which stipulates that 80 new majors should first increase funding for teachers, venues and facilities, and that more than 20 teachers with undergraduate degrees in the same major should be required to meet the teaching needs. Except for the International Football School of Tongji University, which has strong comprehensive teachers, most of the single football specialty integration currently established cannot meet this requirement. Moreover, most of the so-called football colleges established are under the management system of "two brands and one team". Football teachers are not only responsible for the daily teaching of sports education, social sports, leisure sports and sports training, but also for the training of the school football team. At the same time, because college teachers themselves have more tasks such as scientific research, it is inevitable that some of their energy will be diverted. At the same time, according to the Interim Provisions on the Establishment of Ordinary Undergraduate Schools, the number of full-time teachers with graduate education should reach 30%, the number of vice senior teachers should reach 30%, and the number of full-time teachers of full professors should exceed 10%. However, most of the surveyed universities are lower than the undergraduate schools. Teachers' academic qualifications are an important manifestation of scientific research level and knowledge level. Therefore, physical education colleges need to introduce more highly educated and skilled teachers in the future development.

Table 2: List of football teachers in colleges and universities

school name	Number of teachers	The proportion of the number of teachers with various professional titles			
		professor	adjunct professor	lecturer	assistant
Wuhan University Of Sport	14	21.4%	35.7%	42.9%	0.0%
Guangzhou University of Sport	17	14.3%	28.6%	57.1%	8.3%
Nanjing University of Sport	12	14.3%	25.0%	50.0%	0.0%
Tongji University	21	16.7%	19.0%	66.7%	0.0%
Chengdu University	11	9.1%	18.2%	36.4%	36.4%
Changchun Guanghua College	12	16.7%	50.0%	33.3%	0.0%

Football students' daily training time is long and intensity is high, which leads to a greater impact on the performance of athletes' cultural courses, and there is a more serious contradiction between learning and training. The main reasons for the contradiction between learning and training are the improper distribution of the proportion of learning and training, the low scientific level of training, the imperfect policy guarantee system, the imperfect competition system, the blind pursuit of

competitive results, the imperfect school teaching model and other factors. In order to promote the balance of learning and training, it is necessary to enhance the self-administration consciousness of college football students, strengthen the implementation of policies and systems, adopt scientific training means and methods, improve the competition mechanism, establish a correct performance evaluation system, and adopt a reasonable teaching model.

3.4 The toughness of process management is insufficient, and the quality assurance system needs to be improved

Under the background of the country's deepening of football reform and the development of "integration of sports and education", the training of football professionals in colleges and universities should become an important way to deepen the education and selection of football professional competitive talents, and the main training subject to meet the professional needs of football market-oriented reform. The quality and sustainability, scientificity and foresightedness of football talents training in colleges and universities inevitably require the construction of a scientific, reasonable and effective process management system in talent training. Build a comprehensive and scientific system from the aspects of enrollment quality, curriculum quality, teaching quality, learning process management quality, employment quality, etc., control the management quality of each link, and avoid the "cask effect" in process management. Through investigation, it is found that at present, the process management of football major in China's colleges and universities of physical education mainly presents the following three difficulties: first, the talent training program is disconnected from the development of social, political, economic and cultural development. The compatibility between the knowledge, ability and quality requirements of football talent training and the development of the football industry needs to be improved, the talent training program still needs to be revised, and the top level design of process management still needs to pay more attention; Second, the quality of enrollment and source of students needs to be strengthened, and the scientific and forward-looking nature of the enrollment and selection process is insufficient; Thirdly, the standardization, systematicness and scientificity of football teaching management in colleges and universities still need to be improved. The quality assurance construction of football talents training in colleges and universities has not been highly valued by the training subject, the system construction and systematization construction are still relatively lagging behind, and the diversity needs of the football industry and the market and the needs of students' future professional quality are insufficient. Therefore, the review and evaluation of the construction of the quality assurance system of talent training should be strengthened in the review and evaluation of the construction of the football specialty and specialty in colleges and universities of physical education.

4. OPTIMIZATION PATH OF FOOTBALL PROFESSIONAL TALENT TRAINING OF CHENGDU UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY PHYSICAL EDUCATION COLLEGE

It is of great practical significance for the development of the football major and the entire physical education institute of Chengdu University of Technology to examine the current training situation. The focus of the transformation of ideas for the training of football professionals in colleges and universities lies in how to manage to govern, establish a staggered governance of sharing interests and responsibilities, and ensure the innovation of the operation guarantee system in terms of policies, systems and funds.

4.1 The transformation of the idea of training football professionals in the School of Physical Education of Chengdu University of Technology

Through the investigation and development of the current situation of football professional training in physical education colleges of various colleges and universities in China, it is found that the selection and training of football teachers, football coaches and athletes cannot be integrated from the overall level and the internal training linkage level, and the training concept and ideas cannot be optimized by using the laws of career development and the internal laws of talent training. It also failed to examine the current situation of college football professional training from the perspective of international vision and sustainable development. To clarify the question of "who to train", "how to train people" is an important problem to be solved at this stage. Scientific, systematic and complete training ideas are an important link in the training and promotion of football professionals in colleges and universities. At this stage, the football major in colleges and universities should strengthen the joint training mechanism, establish a college - football association or club talent training and training mode of benefit sharing and cooperative training, build a clear concept of talent training, straighten out the past experience in the development of football major in colleges and universities, and gradually explore and issue the development ideas and concepts of football talents with Chinese characteristics. Cultivate basic education football teachers with comprehensive football ability, pay attention to the effective balance of training, learning and competition. The participation of football

matches should not only face the international competition, but also act according to their ability. It should follow the goal and purpose of football professional training in colleges and universities, and should not one-sidedly pursue the competitive level while ignoring the important role of cultural education. The transformation of training ideas and concepts is the key link for the scientific and sustainable development of football talents training in the College of Physical Education of Chengdu University of Technology.

4.2 Recognition of the value orientation of football professional talent training in Chengdu University of Science and Technology Physical Education College

The determination of the value orientation of talent training is the premise to guide the direction and quality of the training of football professionals in colleges and universities. The determination of the value orientation is the criteria and pursuit to define the talent training goals. It can be seen from the analysis and summary of the current situation of football professional training in Chinese colleges and universities that the value of football professional training in many colleges and universities is still to improve the competitive level of college football students. When assessing the effectiveness of football professional training in colleges and universities, it is still based on the improvement of competitive level and the principle of championship. This value concept is divorced from the original intention and mission of colleges and universities to highlight football in recent years. Correct the development path of "professionalism", "competition" and "championship", and adhere to the value orientation of all-round development of talent training. For a long time, the cultivation of sports education talents in China has been divided into two parts. The main reason is that the education department focuses on talent cultivation, and the General Administration of Sport of the People's Republic of China manages the selection and cultivation of professional competitive talents. The "integration of sports and education" has broken the barriers of the past talent training methods and is gradually managed by the education department and the sports department. The transformation of the new concept and new development mode requires a series of reforms in the training of football professionals in colleges and universities, strengthening the deep integration of sports and education, and more importantly, the transformation of the value orientation of football talent training by the society. The value orientation of football talents training in the Physical Education Institute of Chengdu University of Technology should be in line with the development concept of integration of teaching and learning, and promote the reform and development of football talents training in colleges and universities in the new era.

4.3 Synergies of staggered governance in the training of football professionals in the Physical Education Institute of Chengdu University of Technology

Based on the system management theory and the structure function theory, the construction of the football professional talent training system of Chengdu University of Science and Technology Physical Education College requires a governance mechanism of internal and external connection and multi-level coordination to optimize and improve the football professional talent training mechanism.

4.3.1 Benefit sharing

From the perspective of stakeholder theory, the stakeholders in the training of football professionals in colleges and universities are mainly colleges and universities, football students, students' parents, college coaches and sports college cooperative enterprises and clubs. Therefore, from the perspective of stakeholder cooperation, how to tap the role of stakeholders in the talent training system in colleges and universities, and how to reasonably distribute the interests of all parties, is an important topic for the training of football professionals in colleges and universities. From the perspective of students, studying football in colleges and universities not only improves football skills and levels, but also masters the teaching ability of football. From the point of view of coaches, the platform construction of football major in colleges and universities has been brought into play, and athletic achievements and honors have been gained. From the perspective of cooperative enterprises, supporting and sponsoring the training of college football professionals can obtain the benefits of football talent resources and competitive events. Sharing interests and running schools cooperatively are the development path that should be adhered to in the training of football professionals in colleges and universities. In the whole process of training football professionals in colleges and universities, the participation responsibility of all stakeholders should be deepened, the interests and responsibilities should coexist, and the interests of all parties should be reasonably concerned. Only in this way can the training of football professionals in colleges and universities move towards sustainable and systematic development. The principle of ensuring benefit sharing in the talent training management and governance system

is to promote the development of football professional talent training and "integration of sports and education" in Chengdu University of Technology.

4.3.2 Responsibility sharing

What is consistent with the benefit sharing is to adhere to the principle of responsibility sharing. The process management of college football talent training needs to clarify the responsibilities of all stakeholders in each link. The goal of benefit sharing is consistent with that of responsibility sharing. Clarifying responsibility is the central task of college governance. The goal of each link of talent training, grasping the principle, and coordinating interests are important strategies for improving the governance ability of college football talent training. Under the background of the integration of sports and education, the establishment of the training system and mechanism for football professionals in colleges and universities needs to build a negotiation and dialogue mechanism between sports and education departments, break the barriers of the past talent training system and mechanism, jointly optimize and formulate the plan for the training of football professionals in colleges and universities in the new era, and scientifically plan the development path of the training of football professionals in Chinese colleges and universities from an international perspective and a long-term perspective. Specifically, the relevant subjects of football professional talent training in the Sports College of Chengdu University of Technology should work together to clarify the overall awareness of talent training and the concept of responsibility of all parties, pay close attention to the implementation of responsibility, establish an effective communication and negotiation mechanism, and all stakeholders have the right to assume the role of supervision in the process of talent training, build a mechanism for resource allocation and coordination, coordinate the management of the whole process of talent training, and implement the specific objectives of talent training, Promote the construction of a scientific talent training system.

5. SUGGESTIONS FOR OPTIMIZING THE OPERATION GUARANTEE OF FOOTBALL PROFESSIONAL TALENT TRAINING IN THE SCHOOL OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION OF CHENGDU UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

The Ministry of Education of China has made important adjustments to the construction of high-level sports teams in colleges and universities: in principle, there will be no more applications for other sports except football and snow sports. Among the school level representative teams of Chengdu University of Technology, the campus team football project has always been a characteristic traditional university in Sichuan Province, and has made many outstanding achievements over the years. Under the existing conditions, among the full-time teachers of the School of Physical Education of Chengdu University of Technology, there are national high-level referees and referees for supervision; There are also high-level football coaches. Therefore, it has become a feasible path to apply for a high-level football team as a breakthrough for the development of the sports specialty of Chengdu University of Technology. In combination with the macro reform, the establishment of the macro development mechanism of talent training needs to build a scientific and effective security mechanism, starting from the three core links of policy security, system security and funding security, to build a scientific security mechanism and establish a dynamic mechanism for internal and external linkage. The construction of the operation guarantee mechanism for cultivating the whole process management needs to stimulate and mobilize the role of various stakeholders, enhance the role of external resources, and build a scientific guarantee mechanism.

5.1 Policy guarantee

The reform of the training mode of football professionals in colleges and universities urgently needs the top-level design of government departments, the formulation of scientific norms and sustainable security policies, and the strengthening of the deep integration and coordination of education and sports departments. At present, the state has issued relevant policy documents on the integration of sports and education and the cultivation of competitive sports reserve talents from a macro perspective, but there is still a certain gap between the policy implementation and the policy implementation effect and the policy objectives. As the training unit of relevant reserve talents, the Physical Education Institute of Chengdu University of Technology can sort out the institutional obstacles and bottlenecks in all aspects of talent training, grasp the development direction of football reserve talents, learn from foreign scientific management experience, take multiple measures simultaneously, promote the efficiency of policy implementation, build a sound policy implementation supervision mechanism, and provide policy guarantee for talent training.

5.2 System guarantee

As the core of the macro management mechanism, the system guarantee is an important link in the training mechanism and management mechanism of football professionals in colleges and universities. To sum up and analyze the process problems of football teacher education and football competitive talent training in the training of football professionals in colleges and universities, it is necessary to start from the construction of system guarantee, reshape the important position of the system in talent training, establish the approval system of football major construction and football major training system in colleges and universities that are consistent with the requirements of the new era, with in-depth integration of sports and education Evaluation and other institutional links play a leading role in talent training. To establish a scientific system guarantee mechanism, we need to examine various problems in the past policy governance, optimize the content of the system guarantee, standardize the main responsibility, strengthen the effectiveness of policy implementation and implementation, build a scientific and effective mechanism for the joint training and development of the Chengdu University of Technology Sports College, the Football Association and the football club, and formulate a standardized and reasonable selection system for outstanding football talents of the Chengdu University of Technology Sports College, We will build a tutorial system for the growth of football majors in the School of Physical Education of Chengdu University of Technology, establish an international exchange system for football majors in the School of Physical Education of Chengdu University of Technology, and ensure the training quality of football professionals in the School of Physical Education of Chengdu University of Technology from all aspects of the system. At the same time, it is necessary to improve the management and supervision system of the School of Physical Education of Chengdu University of Technology.

5.3 Fund guarantee

From the perspective of system theory, in addition to building a scientific and reasonable operation mechanism in policy and system, the relevant departments should also increase the financial support for the football major of Chengdu University of Technology. Talent training has long-term and hidden social benefits, Therefore, the funding input of all stakeholders in the training of football professionals in the Sports College of Chengdu University of Technology should be scientifically and rationally planned. In the construction of fund guarantee, school investment is the main channel, so we should increase the investment of social funds and actively attract enterprises and all parties to sponsor. It is an important way for social forces to support the development of football cause to provide financial support for the training of football professionals in the Sports College of Chengdu University of Technology. With the guarantee of funds, multi-channel financing and investment in the training of football professionals in the School of Physical Education of Chengdu University of Technology is also an important part of helping the training of Chinese football, Sichuan football and campus football reserve talents.

To sum up, reform and development should be carried out at the same time to ensure the training and operation of football professionals in the School of Physical Education of Chengdu University of Technology. Problems encountered in the development of other universities should be taken as a warning to optimize the development path. We should establish a quality outlook on the cultivation of football reserve talents with the purpose of cultivating students' football teaching and competitive ability and the interests of students' professional development, scientifically explore the development path of talent cultivation in football colleges in colleges and universities from the perspective of the integration of sports and education, and promote the improvement of the quality level of Chinese football professionals.

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